

Questionnaire for strategic experts

Introduction

Thank you for taking part in our study on the challenges facing higher education institutions, with a particular focus on European university alliances. The aim of the study is to identify the main challenges faced by universities involved in alliances in order to help them find more effective solutions.

Your responses will be kept confidential, anonymous and non-traceable. The online interview will be automatically recorded and transcribed by read.ai. Once transcribed, the video will be deleted.

Warm up question:

What are your responsibilities at your university in your current position?

Transformation 1: Mission and expectations

Guiding/input question

Key words (theory driven)

Follow up question (if not answered already)

Question 1

What are the major changes your university has undergone in the past?

From loose to centralized;
from expert to competitive;
more hierarchical; third
mission; diverse arena of
actors; actors of change

Can you assess the success of your university in transforming itself?
What are the most recent changes in your university?
How do you see the so-called third mission* at your university?
Can you describe what the third mission means at your university and what it does in concrete terms?
Which factors do you think contributed to the changes?
**Even though teaching and research are still considered as the pivotal functions of universities, other activities such as technology transfer, lifelong learning or social engagement have broadened the scope of their actions. These activities, labelled as third mission, are supposed to strengthen the impact of science in society and epitomize the changing role of universities (Berghaeuser, H., Hoelscher, M. Reinventing the third mission of higher education in Germany: political frameworks and universities' reactions. Tert Educ Manag 26, 57-76 (2020).)*

Question 2 How do you see the role of the university in relation to societal transitions?	Social change/impact; change agent	Are the SDGs part of the university's strategy, and if so, how are they implied? How do you see the role of the university in relation to the green and digital transition?
Question 3 Is your university competing with other academic actors? If yes, how?	Increased competitiveness	Are there horizontal strategies like specialisation (e.g. SDG)? Are there vertical strategies like university rankings or leagues?

Transformation 2: Organisational structures

Guiding question	Key words (theory driven)	Follow up question (if not answered already)
Question 4 What are the main changes in the general research strategy in recent years?	Centralization, loss of self-guidance, more strategic and hierarchical organisation	How do you deal with top-down research agendas (e.g. SDGs)? How do you deal with the reduced independence of researchers? How do you think researchers could be better involved at the level of university goals and strategies?
Question 5 What are changes you have noticed in recent years in relation to strategic decisions at your university?	Centralization, loss of self-guidance, more strategic and hierarchical organisation	What are the processes now compared to the past? What are the main goals of the university? How do geopolitical factors influence strategic decisions? What is the role of performance indicators in your institution? Have they become more important? Are the positions of decision-makers professionalised?

Transformation 3: Challenges and chances related to the Alliance

Guiding question	Key words (theory driven)	Follow up question (if not answered already)
Question 6	Challenges will be the transformative elements; challenges of alliances are similar to general transformative	To what extent are the challenges associated with your participation in the Alliance similar to the challenges your university has faced in recent years? How are you addressing these challenges?

<p>Where do you see major challenges for your university because of being part of the PIONEER Alliance?</p>	<p>tendencies in the higher education sector</p>	
<p>Question 7 How do you see the PIONEER Alliance impacting your university over the next 6-10 years?</p>	<p>Expert view on the transformative potential and quality of the alliance</p>	<p>Will there be a positive impact or rather a negative one? How will it impact the institutional culture? How will it impact the mission of the university?</p>
<p>Question 8 What will be the added value for your university as a member of the Alliance?</p>	<p>Chances will be potentials for dealing with challenges and expectations</p>	<p>What do you expect from your membership of the PIONEER Alliance?</p>

Questionnaire for operational experts

Introduction

Thank you for participating in our study on challenges related to transformative processes of higher education institutions in general and in relation to participation in European Higher Education Alliances.

Your responses will be kept confidential, anonymous and non-traceable. The online interview will be automatically recorded and transcribed by read.ai. Once transcribed, the video will be deleted.

Warm up question:

What are your responsibilities at your university in your current position?

Transformation 1: Mission and expectations

Guiding/input question	Key words (theory driven)	Follow up question (if not answered already)
<p>Question 1</p> <p>According to you, what are the major changes your university has undergone in the past?</p>	<p>From loose to centralized; from expert to competitive; more hierarchical; third mission; diverse arena of actors; actors of change</p>	<p>Can you assess the success of your university in transforming itself?</p> <p>What are the most recent changes in your university?</p> <p>How do you see the so-called third mission* at your university?</p> <p>Can you describe what the third mission means at your university and what it does in concrete terms?</p> <p>Which factors do you think contributed to the changes?</p> <p><i>*Even though teaching and research are still considered as the pivotal functions of universities, other activities such as technology transfer, lifelong learning or social engagement have broadened the scope of their actions. These activities, labelled as third mission, are supposed to strengthen the impact of science in society and epitomize the changing role of universities (Berghaeuser, H., Hoelscher, M. Reinventing the third mission of higher education in Germany: political frameworks and universities' reactions. Tert Educ Manag 26, 57–76 (2020).)</i></p>
<p>Question 2</p>	<p>Societal change/impact; competitiveness; innovation; stakeholders can be political</p>	<p>How have they changed in recent years?</p> <p>Who are the main stakeholders?</p>

What do different stakeholders expect from the university?	actors (national state, EU, city etc.), economy, society...	
<i>Transformation 2: Organisational structures</i>		
Guiding question	Key words (theory driven)	Follow up question (if not answered already)
Question 3 What changes have you noticed in recent years in relation to academic and non-academic staff?	Professionalisation of staff; reorganization of assessment and recruitment	Has there been a process of professionalisation? Have qualitative assessments been introduced and what do they look like? Have there been changes in the recruitment process? What is the role of university leaders? Who are they?
<i>Transformation 3: Challenges and chances related to the Alliance</i>		
Guiding question	Key words (theory driven)	Follow up question (if not answered already)
Question 4 Where do you see major challenges for your university because of being part of the PIONEER Alliance?	Challenges will be the transformative elements; challenges of alliances are similar to general transformative tendencies in the higher education sector	To what extent are the challenges associated with your participation in the Alliance similar to the challenges your university has faced in recent years? How are you addressing these challenges?
Question 5 How do you see the PIONEER Alliance impacting your university over the next 6-10 years?	Expert view on the transformative potential and quality of the alliance	Will there be a positive impact or rather a negative one? How will it impact the institutional culture? How will it impact the mission of the university?
Question 6 What will be the added value for your university as a member of the Alliance?	Chances will be potentials for dealing with challenges and expectations	What do you expect from your membership of the PIONEER Alliance? How do you see the impact of the Alliance on your university's role in society? To what extent is being part of the Alliance helping you to overcome some of the challenges you have faced in recent years?